

2min
p-peak

7min

Hold 510 min

7-55

2min
p-peak

7-55

Phospho blot

T

REC1

1

GAPDH

T

T

Quick check

gel 3/4

total 5-6

1-50

Fam 1012 Blot
total blot
Setz

Setz Akt + 56 blot Erk blot
55er total blot gel 44

